

Improved asymptotic stability analysis for Lur'e systems with neutral type and time-varying delays

Changchun Shen and Shouming Zhong

Abstract—This paper investigates the problem of absolute stability and robust stability of a class of Lur'e systems with neutral type and time-varying delays. By using Lyapunov direct method and linear matrix inequality technique, new delay-dependent stability criteria are obtained and formulated in terms of linear matrix inequalities (LMIs) which are easy to check the stability of the considered systems. To obtain less conservative stability conditions, an operator is defined to construct the Lyapunov functional. Also, the free weighting matrices approach combining a matrix inequality technique is used to reduce the entailed conservativeness. Numerical examples are given to indicate significant improvements over some existing results.

Keywords—Lur'e system; Linear matrix inequalities; Lyapunov; Stability.

I. INTRODUCTION

TIME delay phenomenon is frequently encountered in many practical systems, such as biological systems, chemical systems, hydraulic systems, nuclear reactor and electrical networks. The Lur'e system, which contains the nonlinear element satisfying certain sector constraints, is an important class of the nonlinear systems. Since Lur'e and Postnikov first proposed the concept of absolute stability as early as the 1940s, the problem of stability of Lur'e systems have been widely studied for several decades, see for example [2-11], and the references therein.

As is well known, Lur'e system with neutral type and time-varying delays being a special case of nonlinear system exists in many dynamic systems, a number of stability conditions have been developed for this type of systems in the past [6, 7, 10]. In [8], delay-independent stability criteria that are based on stability conditions for uncertain Lur'e systems with time delay are presented. Also, there are more concerns on derivation of delay-dependent stability conditions [6, 9], because delay-dependent stability criteria are often less conservative than delay-independent ones when the size of the time-delay is small. However, in each case above, the time delays considered are constant. In [10-11], new delay-dependent stability criteria for Lur'e systems with time-varying delays are obtained. Some methods such as using a free weighting matrix and a bounding technique for cross terms that were developed for stability conditions for linear time delay systems are applied to absolute stability condition for Lur'e systems with time delay. In [10],

Changchun Shen and Shouming Zhong are with the School of Mathematics Science, University Electronic Science and Technology of China, Chengdu 611731, PR China.

Shouming Zhong is with Key Laboratory for NeuroInformation of Ministry of Education, University of Electronic Science and Technology of China, Chengdu 611731, PR China.

Email address: sccyjs2008@163.com.

free weighting matrices for the Newton-Leibniz formula are used. By applying more general Lyapunov-Krasovskii functional, new less conservative delay-dependent stability conditions without using model transformation that often induces additional dynamics [12] are presented in [11]. However, the stability problem for Lur'e systems with neutral type and time-varying delays has not been fully investigated, which motivates this paper.

In this paper, the problem of absolute and robust stability analysis for Lur'e systems with neutral type and time-varying delays is discussed. Since model transformation and bounding techniques for cross terms appearing in the derivative of corresponding Lyapunov functional may introduce additional conservativeness [13], neither model transformation nor bounding technique for cross terms is applied in analyzing the considered systems which may yield less conservative stability conditions. To obtain less conservative stability conditions, an operator $\wp(x_t)$ is defined to construct the Lyapunov functional. Also, the free-weighting matrix approach [14] is employed to further reduce the entailed conservativeness. Numerical examples illustrate the effectiveness and improvement of the obtained results.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider the linear neutral systems with multiple time delay described by following state equation

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) - C\dot{x}(t - \tau(t)) &= Ax(t) + Bx(t - h(t)) + Df(\sigma(t)), \\ \sigma(t) &= Gx(t) + Hx(t - \tau(t)), \\ x(t_0 + \theta) &= \phi(\theta), \quad \forall \theta \in [-\tau^*, 0], \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state vector, $\sigma(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the output vector, $f(\sigma(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the nonlinear function in feedback path, which is denoted as f for simplicity in the sequel, $\phi(\cdot)$ is a differentiable vector-valued initial function, $\tau > 0$ is a constant neutral delay, the discrete delay is $h(t)$ a time-varying function that satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq h(t) \leq h < \infty, \dot{h}(t) \leq h_D < 1, \\ \tau(t) \leq \tau < \infty, \dot{\tau}(t) \leq \tau_D < 1, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where τ, τ_D, h, h_D are constants, $\tau^* = \max(\tau, h)$. $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $D \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ are known constant matrices.

The form of the nonlinear feedback path is formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} f(\sigma(t)) &= [f_1(\sigma_1(t)) \quad f_2(\sigma_2(t)) \quad \cdots \quad f_m(\sigma_m(t))]^T, \\ G &= [g_1 \quad g_2 \quad \cdots \quad g_m]^T, H = [h_1 \quad h_2 \quad \cdots \quad h_m]^T, \\ \sigma(t) &= [\sigma_1(t) \quad \sigma_2(t) \quad \cdots \quad \sigma_m(t)]^T, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$f(\cdot)$ satisfies a sector condition with $f_j(\cdot)$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$, belonging to sectors $[k_j^-, k_j^+]$, i.e.

$$f_j(\cdot) \in K_{[k_j^-, k_j^+]} = \{f_j(\cdot) \mid f_j(0) = 0, (f_j(\sigma_j) - k_j^- \sigma_j) \cdot (f_j(\sigma_j) - k_j^+ \sigma_j) \leq 0, \sigma_j \neq 0\} \quad (4)$$

Remark 1. The constants k_j^- and k_j^+ are allowed to be positive, negative or zero. Hence, the resulting condition is more general than the usual sector condition in [8, 10].

The purpose of this paper is to formulate a practically computable criterion to check the stability of system described by (1)-(4).

III. MAIN RESULT

For the convenience of presentation, we denote

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 &= \text{diag} \{ |k_1^-|, |k_2^-|, \dots, |k_m^-| \}, \\ K_2 &= \text{diag} \{ k_1^+, k_2^+, \dots, k_m^+ \}, \\ K_3 &= \text{diag} \{ k_1^-, k_2^-, \dots, k_m^- \}, \\ K_4 &= \text{diag} \{ k_1^- k_1^+, k_2^- k_2^+, \dots, k_m^- k_m^+ \}. \end{aligned}$$

We define an operator $\varphi : C([- \tau, 0], \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ as: $\varphi(x_t) = x(t) - Cx(t - \tau(t))$.

Remark 2. It can be easily seen that the operator $\varphi(x_t)$ defined in this paper is quite different from the one studied in [6, 21, 22]. In this paper, the neutral delay $\tau(t)$ is a time-varying function, but the operator $\varphi(x_t)$ is always defined when the neutral delay is a known constant delay ([5, 21, 22]). In fact, if we let $\tau(t)$ is a known constant delay, the operator $\varphi(x_t)$ is degenerated into the one considered in [21].

In order to obtain our main results, the following Lemmas and Assumption are needed:

Lemma 1.(Schur Complement). Given constant symmetric matrices $\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2, \Sigma_3$ where $\Sigma_1 = \Sigma_1^T$ and $\Sigma_2 = \Sigma_2^T > 0$, then $\Sigma_1 + \Sigma_3^T \Sigma_2^{-1} \Sigma_3 < 0$ holds if and only if:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_1 & \Sigma_3^T \\ \Sigma_3 & -\Sigma_2 \end{bmatrix} < 0, \text{ or } \begin{bmatrix} -\Sigma_2 & \Sigma_3 \\ \Sigma_3^T & \Sigma_1 \end{bmatrix} < 0.$$

Lemma 2([16]). Assume that $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a}$, $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^{n_b}$ and $N \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a \times n_b}$. Then, for any matrices $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a \times n_b}$, $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a \times n_b}$ and $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a \times n_b}$, the following inequality holds:

$$-2\alpha^T N \beta \leq \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} X & Y - N \\ Y^T - N^T & Z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix}, \text{ if } \begin{bmatrix} X & Y \\ Y^T & Z \end{bmatrix} \geq 0.$$

Lemma 3. Let $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be a vector-valued function with first-order continuous derivative entries, then for any matrices $F = [F_1 \ F_2 \ F_3 \ F_4 \ F_5 \ F_6]$, $Z > 0$ and a scalar $h > 0$, the following inequality holds

$$-\int_{t-h(t)}^t \dot{x}^T(\alpha) Z \dot{x}(\alpha) d\alpha \leq \xi^T(t) \Xi_1 \xi + h \xi^T(t) F^T Z^{-1} F \xi(t)$$

where

$$\xi(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x^T(t) & \dot{x}^T(t) & x^T(t-h(t)) & x^T(t-\tau(t)) \\ \dot{x}^T(t-\tau(t)) & f^T(\sigma(t)) \end{bmatrix}^T$$

$$\Xi_1 = \begin{bmatrix} F_1 + F_1^T & F_2 & -F_1^T + F_3 & F_4 & F_5 & F_6 \\ * & 0 & -F_2^T & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & -F_3^T - F_3 & -F_4 & -F_5 & -F_6 \\ * & * & * & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & * & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Proof: For any matrix $N = [N_1 \ N_2 \ N_3 \ N_4 \ N_5 \ N_6]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= 2[x^T(t)N_1^T + \dot{x}^T(t)N_2^T + x^T(t-h(t))N_3^T \\ &\quad + x^T(t-\tau(t))N_4^T + \dot{x}^T(t-\tau(t))N_5^T + f^T(\sigma(t))N_6^T] \\ &\quad \cdot [x(t) - x(t-h(t)) - \int_{t-h(t)}^t \dot{x}(s)ds] \\ &= 2\xi^T(t)N^T [I \ 0 \ -I \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \xi(t) \\ &\quad - 2 \int_{t-h(t)}^t \xi^T(t)N^T \dot{x}(s)ds \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Employing the matrix inequality $\begin{bmatrix} Z & F \\ F^T & F^T Z^{-1} F \end{bmatrix} \geq 0$ and using Lemma 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} -2 \int_{t-h(t)}^t \xi^T(t)N^T \dot{x}(s)ds &\leq \int_{t-h(t)}^t \dot{x}^T(\alpha) Z \dot{x}(\alpha) d\alpha \\ &\quad + 2\xi^T(t) \cdot [F^T - N^T] [I \ 0 \ -I \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \\ &\quad \cdot \xi(t) + h \xi^T(t) F^T Z^{-1} F \xi(t). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Substituting (5) into (6), we have

$$-\int_{t-h(t)}^t \dot{x}^T(\alpha) Z \dot{x}(\alpha) d\alpha \leq 2\xi^T(t) \Xi_1 \xi(t) + h \xi^T(t) F^T Z^{-1} F \xi(t). \quad (7)$$

where Ξ_1 is the same as defined in Lemma 3. This ends the proof of Lemma 3. ■

Assumption 1. All the eigenvalues of matrix C are inside the unit circle.

3.1 Stability issue

In this section, based on Lyapunov method and linear matrix inequality techniques, following stability criteria are derived.

Theorem 1. Under Assumption 1, the system (1) is asymptotically stable in the sector bounded by (4), if there exist real matrices P_i ($i=2,3,\dots,7$), $F = [F_1 \ F_2 \ F_3 \ F_4 \ F_5 \ F_6]$, M_{12} , M_{14} , M_{24} and S_{12} , symmetric positive definite matrices Z , R , Q , S_{11} , S_{22} and P_1 , symmetric nonnegative definite matrices M_{11} , M_{22} , M_{33} , M_{44} , $\Lambda = \text{diag} \{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_m\}$ and $T = \text{diag} \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ satisfying the following matrix inequalities:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{11} & \Sigma_{12} & \Sigma_{13} & \Sigma_{14} & \Sigma_{15} & \Sigma_{16} & hF_1^T \\ * & \Sigma_{22} & \Sigma_{23} & \Sigma_{24} & \Sigma_{25} & \Sigma_{26} & hF_2^T \\ * & * & \Sigma_{33} & \Sigma_{34} & \Sigma_{35} & \Sigma_{36} & hF_3^T \\ * & * & * & \Sigma_{44} & \Sigma_{45} & \Sigma_{46} & hF_4^T \\ * & * & * & * & \Sigma_{55} & \Sigma_{56} & hF_5^T \\ * & * & * & * & * & \Sigma_{66} & hF_6^T \\ * & * & * & * & * & * & -hZ \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ * & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} > 0, \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & -QC - G^T \Lambda K_1 H & M_{14} \\ * & M_{22} & C^T Q C - H^T \Lambda H & M_{24} \\ * & * & M_{33} & H^T \Lambda \\ * & * & * & M_{44} \end{bmatrix} \geq 0, \quad (10)$$

where $\Sigma_{11} = P_2^T A + A^T P_2 + F_1^T + F_1 + Q A + A^T Q + R + S_{11} + \tau_D M_{11} - 2G^T T K_4 G$, $\Sigma_{12} = P_1 - P_2^T + A^T P_3 + S_{12} + F_2 + G^T \Lambda K_1 G$, $\Sigma_{13} = P_2^T B + A^T P_4 - F_1^T + F_3 + Q B$, $\Sigma_{14} = A^T P_5 + F_4 + \tau_D M_{12} - A^T Q C - 2G^T T K_4 G$, $\Sigma_{15} = P_2^T C + A^T P_6 + F_5$, $\Sigma_{16} = P_2^T D + A^T P_7 + Q D + A^T G^T \Lambda + F_6 + \tau_D M_{14} + G^T T K_2 + G^T T K_3$, $\Sigma_{22} = -P_3 - P_3^T + S_{22} + h Z$, $\Sigma_{23} = P_3^T B - P_4 - F_2^T$, $\Sigma_{24} = G^T \Lambda K_1 H - P_5$, $\Sigma_{25} = P_3^T C - P_6$, $\Sigma_{26} = P_3^T D - P_7$, $\Sigma_{33} = P_4^T B + B^T P_4 - (1 - h_D) R - F_3^T - F_3$, $\Sigma_{34} = B^T P_5 - B^T Q C - F_4$, $\Sigma_{35} = P_4^T C + B^T P_6 - F_5$, $\Sigma_{36} = P_4^T D + B^T P_7 + B^T G^T \Lambda - F_6$, $\Sigma_{44} = \tau_D M_{22} - (1 - \tau_D) S_{11} - 2H^T T K_4 H$, $\Sigma_{45} = P_5^T C - (1 - \tau_D) S_{12}$, $\Sigma_{46} = P_5^T D - C^T Q D + \tau_D M_{24} + H^T T K_2 + H^T T K_3$, $\Sigma_{55} = P_6^T C + C^T P_6 + \tau_D M_{33} - (1 - \tau_D) S_{22}$, $\Sigma_{56} = P_6^T D + C^T P_7 + C^T G^T \Lambda$, $\Sigma_{66} = P_7^T D + D^T P_7 + D^T G^T \Lambda + \Lambda G D + \tau_D M_{44} - 2T$.

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} P_1^T & P_2^T \\ 0 & P_3^T \\ 0 & P_4^T \\ 0 & P_5^T \\ 0 & P_6^T \\ 0 & P_7^T \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ A & -I & B & 0 & C & D \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \Pi = \begin{bmatrix} I \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ C^T \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} Q \begin{bmatrix} A & 0 & B & 0 & 0 & D \end{bmatrix}.$$

$$\dot{V}_2 \leq x^T(t) R x(t) - (1 - h_D) x^T(t - h(t)) R x(t - h(t)) \quad (14)$$

Proof: We choose the following Lyapunov-Krasovskii functional candidate as follows:

$$V = V_1 + V_2 + V_3 + V_4 + V_5 \quad (11)$$

where

$$V_1 = \xi^T(t) E P \xi(t) + \varphi^T(x_t) Q \varphi(x_t),$$

$$V_2 = \int_{t-h(t)}^t x^T(s) R x(s) ds,$$

$$V_3 = \int_{t-\tau(t)}^t \begin{bmatrix} x^T(s) & \dot{x}^T(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ * & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x(s) \\ \dot{x}(s) \end{bmatrix} ds,$$

$$V_4 = \int_{t-h}^t (s - t + h) \dot{x}^T(s) Z \dot{x}(s) ds,$$

$$V_5 = 2 \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i \int_0^{\sigma_i} (f_i(s) + |k_i^-| s) ds,$$

$$E = \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^T,$$

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} P_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ P_2 & P_3 & P_4 & P_5 & P_6 & P_7 \end{bmatrix},$$

where $P_1 > 0$, $R > 0$, $Z > 0$, $\begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ * & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} > 0$, $P_i > 0$ ($i = 2, 3, \dots, 7$) and $\lambda_i \geq 0$ ($i = 2, 3, \dots, m$) are solutions of (8)-(9).

The derivative of along the trajectory of system (1) is given by

$$\dot{V} = \dot{V}_1 + \dot{V}_2 + \dot{V}_3 + \dot{V}_4 + \dot{V}_5. \quad (12)$$

From (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_1 &= 2\xi^T(t) P^T \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + 2\varphi^T(x_t) Q \dot{\varphi}(x_t) \\ &= 2\xi^T(t) P^T \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \\ \begin{pmatrix} Ax(t) - \dot{x}(t) + Bx(t-h(t)) \\ + C\dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) + Df(\sigma(t)) \end{pmatrix} \end{bmatrix} \\ &\quad + 2[x(t) - Cx(t-\tau(t))]^T Q [Ax(t) + Bx(t-h(t)) \\ &\quad + Df(\sigma(t)) + \dot{\tau}(t) C \dot{x}(t-\tau(t))] \\ &= \xi^T(t) (\Gamma + \Gamma^T + \Pi + \Pi^T) \xi(t) + 2\dot{\tau}(t) [x^T(t) \\ &\quad \cdot QC \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) - x^T(t-\tau(t)) C^T QC \dot{x}(t-\tau(t))], \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_3 &\leq \begin{bmatrix} x^T(t) & \dot{x}^T(t) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ * & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x(t) \\ \dot{x}(t) \end{bmatrix} \\ &\quad - (1 - \tau_D) \begin{bmatrix} x^T(t-\tau(t)) & \dot{x}^T(t-\tau(t)) \end{bmatrix} \\ &\quad \cdot \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ S_{12}^T & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x(t-\tau(t)) \\ \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) \end{bmatrix} \\ &= x^T(t) S_{11} x(t) + 2x^T(t) S_{12} \dot{x}(t) + \dot{x}^T(t) S_{22} \dot{x}(t) \\ &\quad - (1 - \tau_D) x^T(t-\tau(t)) S_{11} x(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad - 2(1 - \tau_D) x^T(t-\tau(t)) S_{12} \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad - (1 - \tau_D) \dot{x}^T(t-\tau(t)) S_{22} \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_4 &\leq h \dot{x}^T(t) Z \dot{x}(t) - \int_{t-h(t)}^t \dot{x}^T(s) Z \dot{x}(s) ds \\ &\leq h \dot{x}^T(t) Z \dot{x}(t) + \xi^T(t) \Xi_1 \xi(t) + h \xi^T(t) F^T Z^{-1} F \xi(t) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_5 &= 2 \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i [f_i(\sigma_i) + |k_i^-| (g_i^T x(t) + h_i^T x(t-\tau(t)))] \\ &\quad \cdot [g_i^T \dot{x}(t) + h_i^T \dot{x}(t-\tau(t))] \\ &= 2f^T(\sigma(t)) \Lambda G [Ax(t) + Bx(t-h(t)) + C\dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad + Df(\sigma(t))] + 2x^T(t) G^T \Lambda K_1 G \dot{x}(t) + 2\dot{x}^T(t) G^T \Lambda \\ &\quad \cdot K_1 H x(t-\tau(t)) + 2\dot{\tau}(t) [x^T(t) G^T \Lambda K_1 H \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad + x^T(t-\tau(t)) H^T \Lambda H \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad + \dot{x}^T(t-\tau(t)) H^T \Lambda f(\sigma(t))]. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Using the condition (2), it holds

$$\begin{aligned} &2\dot{\tau}(t) [x^T(t) QC \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) - x^T(t-\tau(t)) C^T QC \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad + x^T(t) G^T \Lambda K_1 H \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) + x^T(t-\tau(t)) H^T \Lambda H \\ &\quad \cdot \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) + x^T(t-\tau(t)) H^T \Lambda f(\sigma(t))] \\ &\leq (\tau_D - \dot{\tau}(t)) [x^T(t) M_{11} x(t) + 2x^T(t) M_{12} x(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad + 2x^T(t) M_{14} f(\sigma(t)) + x^T(t-\tau(t)) M_{22} x(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad + 2x^T(t-\tau(t)) M_{24} f(\sigma(t)) + \dot{x}^T(t-\tau(t)) M_{33} \\ &\quad \cdot \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) + f^T(\sigma(t)) M_{44} f(\sigma(t))] + 2\dot{\tau}(t) x^T(t) \\ &\quad \cdot [QC + G^T \Lambda K_1 H] \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) + 2\dot{\tau}(t) x^T(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad \cdot [H^T \Lambda H - C^T QC] \dot{x}(t-\tau(t)) + 2\dot{\tau}(t) \dot{x}^T(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad \cdot H^T \Lambda f(\sigma(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where M_{11} , M_{12} , M_{14} , M_{22} , M_{24} , M_{33} and M_{44} are solutions of (10). Since the nonlinearities $f_j(\cdot)$ satisfy the constraint (4),

for any $T = \text{diag}\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\} \geq 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &\leq -2 \sum_{j=1}^m t_j (f_j(\sigma_j) - k_j^- \sigma_j)(f_j(\sigma_j) - k_j^+ \sigma_j) \\
 &= -2x^T(t)G^T T K_4 G x(t) - 4x^T(t)G^T T K_4 G x(t - \tau(t)) \\
 &\quad + 2x^T(t)[G^T T K_2 + G^T T K_3]f(\sigma(t)) - 2x^T(t - \tau(t)) \\
 &\quad \cdot H^T T K_4 H x(t - \tau(t)) + 2x^T(t - \tau(t))[H^T T K_2 \\
 &\quad + H^T T K_3]f(\sigma(t)) - 2f^T(\sigma(t))Tf(\sigma(t))
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Calculating the derivative of V along the solution of system (1) and adding the terms on the right of (19) into \dot{V} yield

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{V} &\leq \xi^T(t)\Phi\xi(t) + h\xi^T(t)F^T Z^{-1}F\xi(t) - \dot{\tau}(t)\zeta^T(t) \\
 &\quad \cdot \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & -QC - G^T \Lambda K_1 H & M_{14} \\ * & M_{22} & C^T Q C - H^T \Lambda H & M_{24} \\ * & * & M_{33} & H^T \Lambda \\ * & * & * & M_{44} \end{bmatrix} \zeta(t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \zeta(t) &= [x^T(t) \quad x^T(t - \tau(t)) \quad \dot{x}^T(t - \tau(t)) \quad f^T(\sigma(t))]^T, \\
 \Phi &= \begin{bmatrix} \Phi_{11} & \Phi_{12} & \Phi_{13} & \Phi_{14} & \Phi_{15} & \Phi_{16} \\ * & \Phi_{22} & \Phi_{23} & \Phi_{24} & \Phi_{25} & \Phi_{26} \\ * & * & \Phi_{33} & \Phi_{34} & \Phi_{35} & \Phi_{36} \\ * & * & * & \Phi_{44} & \Phi_{45} & \Phi_{46} \\ * & * & * & * & \Phi_{55} & \Phi_{56} \\ * & * & * & * & * & \Phi_{66} \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi_{ij} = \Sigma_{ij}$ for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 7$, Σ_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 7$) are the same as defined in the Theorem 1.

A sufficient condition for asymptotically stability of system (1) is that the operator $\wp(x_t)$ is stability and there exist real matrices P_i ($i=2,3,\dots,7$), $F = [F_1 \ F_2 \ F_3 \ F_4 \ F_5 \ F_6]$, M_{12} , M_{14} , M_{24} and S_{12} , symmetric positive definite matrices Z , R , Q , S_{11} , S_{22} and P_1 , symmetric nonnegative definite matrices M_{11} , M_{22} , M_{33} , M_{44} , $\Lambda = \text{diag}\{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_m\}$ and $T = \text{diag}\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ such that

$$\dot{V} \leq \xi^T(t)\Phi\xi(t) + h\xi^T(t)F^T Z^{-1}F\xi(t) < 0 \tag{21}$$

for all $\xi(t) \neq 0$. Thus, using Lemma 1, it is easy to check that LMIs (8)-(10) is equivalent to LMI (21). It is well known that Assumption 1 guarantees the stability of different system $x(t) - Cx(t - \tau(t)) = 0$. Therefore, system described by (1)-(4) is asymptotically stable according to Theorem 8.1 in [1]. This completes the proof. ■

When the nonlinear function satisfying:

$$f_j(\cdot) \in K_{[0, \infty]} = \{f_j(\cdot) | f_j(0) = 0, \sigma_j f_j(\sigma_j) > 0, \sigma_j \neq 0\} \tag{22}$$

which is located in a finite sector $[0, \infty]$, Theorem 2 is presented as follows.

Theorem 2. Under Assumption 1, the system (1) is asymptotically stable in the sector bounded by (22), if there exist real matrices M_{12} , M_{14} , M_{24} , S_{12} , P_i ($i=2,3,\dots,7$) and $F = [F_1 \ F_2 \ F_3 \ F_4 \ F_5 \ F_6]$, symmetric positive definite matrices Z , R , Q , S_{11} , S_{22} and P_1 , symmetric nonnegative definite matrices M_{11} , M_{22} , M_{33} , M_{44} , $\Lambda =$

$\text{diag}\{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_m\}$ and $T = \text{diag}\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ satisfying the following matrix inequality:

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_{11} & \Sigma_{12} & \Sigma_{13} & E_{14} & \Sigma_{15} & E_{16} & hF_1^T \\ * & \Sigma_{22} & \Sigma_{23} & \Sigma_{24} & \Sigma_{25} & \Sigma_{26} & hF_2^T \\ * & * & \Sigma_{33} & \Sigma_{34} & \Sigma_{35} & \Sigma_{36} & hF_3^T \\ * & * & * & E_{44} & \Sigma_{45} & E_{46} & hF_4^T \\ * & * & * & * & \Sigma_{55} & \Sigma_{56} & hF_5^T \\ * & * & * & * & * & E_{66} & hF_6^T \\ * & * & * & * & * & * & -hZ \end{bmatrix} < 0 \tag{23}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ * & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} > 0, \tag{24}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & -QC - G^T \Lambda K_1 H & M_{14} \\ * & M_{22} & C^T Q C - H^T \Lambda H & M_{24} \\ * & * & M_{33} & H^T \Lambda \\ * & * & * & M_{44} \end{bmatrix} \geq 0, \tag{25}$$

where Σ_{ij} , ($i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6$) are the same as defined in the Theorem 1 and $E_{11} = P_2^T A + A^T P_2 + F_1^T + F_1 + Q A + A^T Q + R + S_{11} + \tau_D M_{11}$, $E_{14} = A^T P_5 + F_4 + \tau_D M_{12} - A^T Q C$, $E_{16} = P_2^T D + A^T P_7 + Q D + A^T G^T \Lambda + F_6 + \tau_D M_{14} + G^T T$, $E_{44} = \tau_D M_{22} - (1 - \tau_D) S_{11}$, $E_{46} = P_5^T D - C^T Q D$, $E_{66} = P_7^T D + D^T P_7 + D^T G^T \Lambda + \Lambda G D + \tau_D M_{44} + H^T T$.

Proof: For neutral system (1) with nonlinearity located in the sector, that is the nonlinear function satisfying, we have

$$2 \sum_{j=1}^m t_j f_j(\sigma_j(t)) g_j^T x(t) \geq 0, j = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{26}$$

where t_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, m$), the proof of stability conditions (23)-(25) follow the similar line as that in Theorem 1 unless calculating the derivative of V along the solution of system (1) and adding the terms on the right of (19) is replaced by (26) into \dot{V} , respectively. And the results (23)-(25) are produced by the uniform approach to the later proof of Theorem 1. ■

3.2 Robust stability

In this section, we extend the obtained stability conditions to robust stability problem for uncertain Lur'e system with neutral type

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{x}(t) &= (A + \Delta A(t))x(t) + (B + \Delta B(t))x(t - h(t)) \\
 &\quad + (D + \Delta D(t))f(\sigma(t)) + (C + \Delta C(t))\dot{x}(t - \tau(t)), \\
 \sigma(t) &= Gx(t) + Hx(t - \tau(t)), \\
 x(t_0 + \theta) &= \phi(\theta), \quad \forall \theta \in [-\tau^*, 0],
 \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

where A , B , C and D follow the same definitions of those as in system (1). $\Delta A(t)$, $\Delta B(t)$, $\Delta C(t)$ and $\Delta D(t)$ are the parametric uncertainties in the system, which are assumed to be of the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta A(t) & \Delta B(t) & \Delta C(t) & \Delta D(t) \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \end{bmatrix} = LK(t) \begin{bmatrix} E_a & E_b & E_c & E_d \end{bmatrix} \tag{28}$$

where $K(t)$ is an unknown real and possibly time-varying matrix with Lebesgue measurable elements satisfying

$$K^T(t)K(t) \leq I, \tag{29}$$

and L , E_a , E_b , E_c and E_d are known real constant matrices which characterize how the uncertainty enters the nominal

matrices A, B, C and D .

Before proceeding further, system (25) can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) - C\dot{x}(t - \tau) &= Ax(t) + Bx(t - h(t)) \\ &\quad + Df(\sigma(t)) + Lu, \\ z &= E_a x(t) + E_b x(t - h(t)) \\ &\quad + E_c \dot{x}(t - \tau) + E_d f(\sigma(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

with the constraint: $u = K(t)z$.

We further have:

$$u^T u \leq [E_a x(t) + E_b x(t - h(t)) + E_c \dot{x}(t - \tau) + E_d f(\sigma(t))]^T \cdot [E_a x(t) + E_b x(t - h(t)) + E_c \dot{x}(t - \tau) + E_d f(\sigma(t))]. \quad (31)$$

Using the similar method in the proof of Lemma 3, we can obtain the following Lemma

Lemma 4. Let $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be a vector-valued function with first-order continuous derivative entries, then for any matrices $F = [F_1 \ F_2 \ F_3 \ F_4 \ F_5 \ F_6 \ F_7]$, $Z > 0$ and a scalar $h > 0$, the following inequality holds

$$-\int_{t-h(t)}^t \dot{x}^T(\alpha) Z \dot{x}(\alpha) d\alpha \leq q^T(t) \Xi_2 q(t) + h \xi^T(t) F^T Z^{-1} F \xi(t)$$

where $\xi(t) = [x^T(t) \ \dot{x}^T(t) \ x^T(t - h(t)) \ x^T(t - \tau(t)) \ \dot{x}^T(t - \tau(t)) \ f^T(\sigma(t)) \ u^T]^T$ and $\Xi_2 =$

$$\begin{bmatrix} F_1 + F_1^T & F_2 & -F_1^T + F_3 & F_4 & F_5 & F_6 & F_7 \\ * & 0 & -F_2^T & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & -F_3^T - F_3 & -F_4 & -F_5 & -F_6 & -F_7 \\ * & * & * & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & * & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & * & * & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Base on Theorem 1, we can perform the robust stability analysis for uncertain neutral system (27).

Theorem 3. Under Assumption 1, the system (27) is asymptotically stable in the sector bounded by (4), if there exist real matrices P_i ($i=2,3,\dots,8$), $F = [F_1 \ F_2 \ F_3 \ F_4 \ F_5 \ F_6 \ F_7]$, M_{12} , M_{14} , M_{24} and S_{12} , symmetric positive definite matrices Z, R, Q, S_{11}, S_{22} and P_1 , symmetric nonnegative definite matrices $M_{11}, M_{22}, M_{33}, M_{44}, \Lambda = \text{diag}\{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_m\}$ and $T = \text{diag}\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ satisfying the following matrix inequality:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Omega_{11} & \Omega_{12} & \Omega_{13} \\ * & -hZ & 0 \\ * & * & -\varepsilon I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (32)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ * & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} > 0, \quad (33)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & -QC - G^T \Lambda K_1 H & M_{14} \\ * & M_{22} & C^T Q C - H^T \Lambda H & M_{24} \\ * & * & M_{33} & H^T \Lambda \\ * & * & * & M_{44} \end{bmatrix} \geq 0, \quad (34)$$

where

$$\Omega_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\Sigma}_{11} & \hat{\Sigma}_{12} & \hat{\Sigma}_{13} & \hat{\Sigma}_{14} & \hat{\Sigma}_{15} & \hat{\Sigma}_{16} & \hat{\Sigma}_{17} \\ * & \hat{\Sigma}_{22} & \hat{\Sigma}_{23} & \hat{\Sigma}_{24} & \hat{\Sigma}_{25} & \hat{\Sigma}_{26} & \hat{\Sigma}_{27} \\ * & * & \hat{\Sigma}_{33} & \hat{\Sigma}_{34} & \hat{\Sigma}_{35} & \hat{\Sigma}_{36} & \hat{\Sigma}_{37} \\ * & * & * & \hat{\Sigma}_{44} & \hat{\Sigma}_{45} & \hat{\Sigma}_{46} & \hat{\Sigma}_{47} \\ * & * & * & * & \hat{\Sigma}_{55} & \hat{\Sigma}_{56} & \hat{\Sigma}_{57} \\ * & * & * & * & * & \hat{\Sigma}_{66} & \hat{\Sigma}_{67} \\ * & * & * & * & * & * & \hat{\Sigma}_{77} \end{bmatrix}$$

and $\hat{\Sigma}_{i,j} = \Sigma_{i,j}$ ($i,j=1,2,\dots,6$), $\Sigma_{i,j}$ ($i,j=1,2,\dots,6$) are the same as defined in the Theorem 1, and $\hat{\Sigma}_{17} = P_2^T L - A^T P_8 + QL + F_7$, $\hat{\Sigma}_{27} = P_3^T L - P_8$, $\hat{\Sigma}_{37} = P_4^T L + B^T P_8 - F_7$, $\hat{\Sigma}_{47} = P_5^T L - C^T QL$, $\hat{\Sigma}_{57} = P_6^T L + C^T P_8$, $\hat{\Sigma}_{67} = P_7^T L + D^T P_8 + \Lambda GL$ and $\hat{\Sigma}_{77} = P_8^T L + L^T P_8 - \varepsilon I$.

Proof of Theorem 3. Applying the similar method in the proof of Theorem 1, we can obtain

$$\dot{V} \leq q^T(t) \hat{\Phi} q(t) + h q^T(t) F^T Z^{-1} F q(t) - \dot{\tau}(t) \zeta^T(t) \zeta(t)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & -QC - G^T \Lambda K_1 H & M_{14} \\ * & M_{22} & C^T Q C - H^T \Lambda H & M_{24} \\ * & * & M_{33} & H^T \Lambda \\ * & * & * & M_{44} \end{bmatrix} \zeta(t) \quad (35)$$

where

$$\zeta(t) = [x^T(t) \ x^T(t - \tau(t)) \ \dot{x}^T(t - \tau(t)) \ f^T(\sigma(t))]^T,$$

$$\hat{\Phi} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\Phi}_{11} & \hat{\Phi}_{12} & \hat{\Phi}_{13} & \hat{\Phi}_{14} & \hat{\Phi}_{15} & \hat{\Phi}_{16} & \hat{\Sigma}_{17} \\ * & \hat{\Phi}_{22} & \hat{\Phi}_{23} & \hat{\Phi}_{24} & P_3^T C - P_6 & c\Phi_{26} & \hat{\Sigma}_{27} \\ * & * & \hat{\Phi}_{33} & \hat{\Phi}_{34} & \hat{\Phi}_{35} & \hat{\Phi}_{36} & \hat{\Sigma}_{37} \\ * & * & * & \hat{\Phi}_{44} & \hat{\Phi}_{45} & \hat{\Phi}_{46} & \hat{\Sigma}_{47} \\ * & * & * & * & \hat{\Phi}_{55} & \hat{\Phi}_{56} & \hat{\Sigma}_{57} \\ * & * & * & * & * & \hat{\Phi}_{66} & \hat{\Sigma}_{67} \\ * & * & * & * & * & * & \hat{\Sigma}_{77} \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\Omega_{12} = [hF_1^T \ hF_2 \ hF_3 \ hF_4 \ hF_5 \ hF_6 \ hF_7]^T$, $\Omega_{13} = [\varepsilon E_a \ 0 \ \varepsilon E_b \ 0 \ \varepsilon E_c \ \varepsilon E_d \ 0]^T$, $\hat{\Phi}_{ij} = \Sigma_{ij}$ ($i,j=1,2,\dots,6$), Σ_{ij} ($i,j=1,2,\dots,6$) are the same as defined in the Theorem 1, $\hat{\Phi}_{k7}$ ($k=1,2,\dots,6$) are the same as defined in the Theorem 3 and $\hat{\Sigma}_{77} = P_8^T L + L^T P_8$.

A sufficient condition for asymptotically stability of system (25) is that there exist real matrices P_i ($i=2,3,\dots,8$), $F = [F_1 \ F_2 \ F_3 \ F_4 \ F_5 \ F_6 \ F_7]$, M_{12} , M_{14} , M_{24} and S_{12} , symmetric positive definite matrices Z, R, Q, S_{11}, S_{22} and P_1 , symmetric nonnegative definite matrices $M_{11}, M_{22}, M_{33}, M_{44}, \Lambda = \text{diag}\{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_m\}$ and $T = \text{diag}\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$, such that

$$\dot{V} \leq q^T(t) \hat{\Phi} q(t) + h q^T(t) F^T Z^{-1} F q(t) < 0 \quad (36)$$

for all $q(t) \neq 0$. Using the S-procedure in [1], one can see that this condition is implied by the existence of nonnegative scalar $\varepsilon > 0$ such that

$$q^T(t) \Phi q(t) + h q^T(t) F^T Z^{-1} F q(t) + \varepsilon \{ [E_a x(t) + E_b x(t - h(t)) + E_c \dot{x}(t - \tau(t)) + E_d f(\sigma(t))]^T \cdot [E_a x(t) + E_b x(t - h(t)) + E_c \dot{x}(t - \tau(t)) + E_d f(\sigma(t))] - u^T u \} < 0 \quad (37)$$

for all $q(t) \neq 0$. By using Lemma 1, the matrix inequalities (30)-(31) imply (34). It is well known that Assumption 1 guarantees the stability of different system $x(t) - Cx(t - \tau) = 0$. Therefore, system (25) is robustly asymptotically stable according to Theorem 8.1 in [2]. This completes the proof.

While the nonlinear system (25) which is located in a sector $[0, \infty]$, condition for robust stability analysis of uncertain system (25) is obtained in Theorem 4.

Theorem 4. Under Assumption 1, the system (1) is asymptotically stable in the sector bounded by (21), if there exist real matrices P_i ($i=2,3,\dots,8$), $F = [F_1 F_2 F_3 F_4 F_5 F_6 F_7]$, M_{12} , M_{14} , M_{24} and S_{12} , symmetric positive definite matrices Z , R , Q , S_{11} , S_{22} and P_1 , symmetric nonnegative definite matrices M_{11} , M_{22} , M_{33} , M_{44} , $\Lambda = \text{diag}\{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_m\}$ and $T = \text{diag}\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ satisfying the following matrix inequality:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\Omega}_{11} & \hat{\Omega}_{12} & \hat{\Omega}_{13} \\ * & -hZ & 0 \\ * & * & -\varepsilon I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (38)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ * & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} > 0, \quad (39)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & -QC - G^T \Lambda K_1 H & M_{14} \\ * & M_{22} & C^T Q C - H^T \Lambda H & M_{24} \\ * & * & M_{33} & H^T \Lambda \\ * & * & * & M_{44} \end{bmatrix} \geq 0, \quad (40)$$

where

$$\hat{\Omega}_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{E}_{11} & \hat{E}_{12} & \hat{E}_{13} & \hat{E}_{14} & \hat{E}_{15} & \hat{E}_{16} & \hat{E}_{17} \\ * & \hat{E}_{22} & \hat{E}_{23} & \hat{E}_{24} & \hat{E}_{25} & \hat{E}_{26} & \hat{E}_{27} \\ * & * & \hat{E}_{33} & \hat{E}_{34} & \hat{E}_{35} & \hat{E}_{36} & \hat{E}_{37} \\ * & * & * & \hat{E}_{44} & \hat{E}_{45} & \hat{E}_{46} & \hat{E}_{47} \\ * & * & * & * & \hat{E}_{55} & \hat{E}_{56} & \hat{E}_{57} \\ * & * & * & * & * & \hat{E}_{66} & \hat{E}_{67} \\ * & * & * & * & * & * & \hat{E}_{77} \end{bmatrix}$$

and $\hat{\Omega}_{12} = [hF_1^T \ hF_2 \ hF_3 \ hF_4 \ hF_5 \ hF_6 \ hF_7]^T$, $\hat{\Omega}_{13} = [\varepsilon E_a \ 0 \ \varepsilon E_b \ 0 \ \varepsilon E_c \ \varepsilon E_d \ 0]^T$, $\hat{E}_{ij} = E_{ij}$ ($i,j=1,2,\dots,6$), E_{ij} ($i,j=1,2,\dots,6$) are the same as defined in the Theorem 2, and $\hat{E}_{17} = P_2^T L - A^T P_8 + QL + F_7$, $\hat{E}_{27} = P_3^T L - P_8$, $\hat{E}_{37} = P_4^T L + B^T P_8 - F_7$, $\hat{E}_{47} = P_5^T L - C^T QL$, $\hat{E}_{57} = P_6^T L + C^T P_8$, $\hat{E}_{67} = P_7^T L + D^T P_8 + \Lambda GL$ and $\hat{E}_{77} = P_8^T L + L^T P_8 - \varepsilon I$.

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The following numerical examples are presented to illustrate the usefulness of the proposed theoretical results given in Section 2 and 3.

Example 1. Consider the lur'e system with neutral type with following parameters:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0.5 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.4 \\ 0.4 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, C = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} -0.5 \\ -0.75 \end{bmatrix},$$

TABLE I

THE MAXIMUM UPPER BOUND DELAYS h OF EXAMPLE 1 WITH $\tau_D = 0.1$

h_D	0.00	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80
h in [10]	4.7407	2.2424	1.5434	0.9888	0.7228
h in this paper	Any	Any	Any	1.9991	1.0106

TABLE II

THE MAXIMUM UPPER BOUND DELAYS h OF EXAMPLE 1 WITH $\tau_D = 0.5$

h_D	0.00	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80
h in [10]	3.0562	1.8344	1.3029	0.7793	0.6282
h in this paper	Any	Any	Any	1.7376	0.9017

$$G = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2 \\ 0.6 \end{bmatrix}^T \text{ and } H = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^T.$$

Where the system matrices considered here are of the same parameters as that in Example 2 of [15] and Example 1 of [10]. Since the nonlinearity is different, the method in [15] could not be used here. Using the Theorem 1 in this paper, the maximum upper bound delays h for stability of system (25) are listed in the following tables for different value of h_D . In Table 1, we let $\tau_D = 0.1$; in Table 2, we let $\tau_D = 0.5$; in Table 3, we let $\tau_D = 0.9$. It is clear to see that the results in this paper are much less conservative than those in [10].

Example 2. Since system of retard type can be viewed as a special case of neutral system, consider the system (25) with the same parameters as in [10, 17, 18].

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 \\ -1 & -2 \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} -0.2 & -0.5 \\ 0.5 & -0.2 \end{bmatrix}, C = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} -0.2 \\ -0.3 \end{bmatrix}, G = \begin{bmatrix} 0.6 \\ 0.8 \end{bmatrix}^T, H = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^T, h_D = 0,$$

$$L = E_a = E_b = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.1 \end{bmatrix}, E_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$E_d = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, K(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\omega t) & 0 \\ 0 & \sin(\omega t) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using Theorems 3 or 4, the maximum upper bound delay h of the system (25) with nonlinearity satisfying (4) or (21) in this paper and methods in [10, 17, 18] is listed in Table 4. It shows that the method in this paper produces better result than [17, 18].

Example 3. Consider the system described by (27) with

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.9 \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, C = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} -0.2 \\ -0.3 \end{bmatrix}, G = \begin{bmatrix} 0.6 \\ 0.8 \end{bmatrix}^T, H = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^T, L = E_a =$$

$$E_b = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.1 \end{bmatrix}, E_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, E_d = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, K(t) =$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sin(\omega t) & 0 \\ 0 & \sin(\omega t) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using Theorem 2 or 4, the maximum upper bound delay h of the system (25) with nonlinearity satisfying (4) is listed in Table 5. And methods in [10, 19, 20] are compared with our results in the Table. It shows that the method in this paper is more effective.

V. CONCLUSION

In This paper, the problem of absolute stability and robust stability of a class of Lur'e systems with neutral type is

TABLE III

THE MAXIMUM UPPER BOUND DELAYS h OF EXAMPLE 1 WITH $\tau_D = 0.9$

h_D	0.00	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80
h in [10]	1.7376	0.1085	0.1019	0.0983	0.0967
h in this paper	1.1285	0.8996	0.6378	0.5679	0.3389

TABLE IV

THE MAXIMUM UPPER BOUND DELAYS h OF EXAMPLE 2

h_D	$f_j(\cdot) \in K[0, 0.5]$	$f_j(\cdot) \in K[0, 10000]$	$f_j(\cdot) \in K[0, \infty]$
Nian [17]	0.3053	—	—
Yang et al. [18]	—	—	2.055
He [9]	99899999	9989993	—
Gao et al. [10]	Any	Any	Any
h in this paper	Any	Any	Any

TABLE V

THE MAXIMUM UPPER BOUND DELAYS h OF EXAMPLE 3

h_D	$f_j(\cdot) \in K[0, 0.5]$	$f_j(\cdot) \in K[0, 10000]$	$f_j(\cdot) \in K[0, \infty]$
Yu et al. [19]	2.312	—	2.055
Han [20]	2.449	—	—
Gao et al. [10]	Any	Any	4.158
h in this paper	Any	Any	4.426

investigated. Sufficient conditions are given in terms of linear matrix inequalities which can be easily solved by LMI Toolbox in Matlab. Numerical examples are given to indicate significant improvements over some existing results.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by National Basic Research Program of China (2010CB732501) and UESTC Research Fund For Youth Science & Technology (L08010701JX0809).

REFERENCES

- [1] J. K. Hale, S. M. & Verduyn Lunel Introduction to functional differential equation. New York: Springer 1993:292-293
- [2] S. Boyd, L.El. Ghaoui, E. Feron, &V. Balakrishnan, Linear matrix inequalities in systems and control theory. Philadelphia: SIAM 1994.
- [3] H. Miyagi, K. Yamashita, Stability studies of control systems using a non-Lur'e type Lyapunov function. *IEEE Trans. Automat. Control* 1986;31:970-972.
- [4] T. Li, J.J. Yu, Z. Wang, Delay-range-dependent synchronization criterion for Lure systems with delay feedback control. *Communications in Nonlinear Science and Numerical Simulation* 2009;14:1796-1803.
- [5] S.M. Lee, Ju H. Park, Delay-dependent criteriaforabsolutestabilityof uncertain time-delayedLuredynamicalsystems. *Journal of the Franklin Institute* 2010;347:146-153.
- [6] Q.-L. Han, A new delay-dependent absolute stability criterion for a class of nonlinear neutral systems. *Automatica* 2008;44:272-277.
- [7] S. M. Lee, O. M. Kwon, Ju H. Park, Novel robust delay dependent criterion for absolute stability of Lur'e of neutral type. *Modern Physics Letters B (MPLB)* 2009;23:1641-1650.
- [8] Y. He, M. Wu, Absolute stability for multiple delay general Lur'e control systems with multiple nonlinearities. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics* 2003;159:241-248.
- [9] Y. He, M. Wu, J.-H. She, Guo-Ping Liu, Robust stability for delay Lur'e control systems with multiple nonlinearities. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics* 2005;176:371-380.
- [10] J.F. Gao, H.Y. Su, Xiaofu Ji, Jian Chu, Stability analysis for a class of neutral systems with mixed delays and sector-bounded nonlinearity. *Nonlinear Analysis: Real World Applications* 2008;9:2350-2360.
- [11] S.J. Choi, S.M. Lee, S.C. Won, Ju H. Park, Improved delay-dependent stability criteria for uncertain Lur'e systems with sector and slope restricted nonlinearities and time-varying delays. *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 2009;208:520-530.
- [12] K. Gu, V.L. Kharitonov, J. Chen, Stability of Time-Delay Systems. Birkhauser, Boston, 2003.
- [13] K.Q. Gu, S.I. Niculescu, Additional dynamics in transformed time-delay systems. *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control* 2000;45:572-575.
- [14] D.Y. Liu, X.Z. Liu, S.M. Zhong, Delay-dependent robust stability and control synthesis for uncertain switched neutral systems with mixed delays. *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 2008;202:828-839.
- [15] J.H. Park, Novel robust stability criterion for a class of neutral systems with mixed delays and nonlinear perturbations. *Appl. Math. Comput.* 2005;161:413-421.
- [16] W.-H. Chen, W. X. Zheng. Delay-dependent robust stabilization for uncertain neutral systems with distributed delays. *Automatica* 2007;43:95-104.

- [17] X.H. Nian, Delay dependent conditions for absolute stability of Lurie type control systems. *Acta Automatica Sin.* 1999;25:564-566.
- [18] B. Yang, J.C. Wang, Delay-dependent criterion for absolute stability of neutral general lurie systems, *Acta Automatica Sin.* 2004;30:261-264.
- [19] L. Yu, Q.L. Han, S.M. Yu, J.F. Gao, Delay-dependent conditions for robust absolute stability of uncertain time-delay systems. *Proceedings of the 42nd IEEE Conference on Decision and Control* 2003:6033-6037.
- [20] Q.L. Han, Absolute stability of time-delay systems with sector-bounded nonlinearity. *Automatica* 2005;41:2171-2176.
- [21] F. Qiu, B.T. Cui, Y. Ji, Novel robust stability analysis for uncertain neutral system with mixed delays, *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals* 42 (2009) 1820-1828 .
- [22] L.L. Xiong, S.M. Zhong, J.K. Tian, Novel robust stability criteria of uncertain neutral systems with discrete and distributed delays, *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals* 40 (2009) 771-777.

Changchun Shen was born in Sichuan Province, China, in 1982. He received the B.S. degree from Sichuan Normal University, Chengdu, in 2005. and the M.S. degree from University of Electronic Science and Technology of China, Sichuan in 2008, both in applied mathematics. He is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with UESTC. His research interests include chaos synchronization, medical image processing and delay dynamic systems.

Shouming Zhong was born in 1955 in Sichuan, China. He received B.S. degree in applied mathematics from UESTC, Chengdu, China, in 1982. From 1984 to 1986, he studied at the Department of Mathematics in Sun Yatsen University, Guangzhou, China. From 2005 to 2006, he was a visiting research associate with the Department of Mathematics in University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Canada. He is currently as a full professor with School of Applied Mathematics, UESTC. His current research interests include differential equations, neural networks, biomathematics and robust control. He has authored more than 80 papers in reputed journals such as the International Journal of Systems Science, Applied Mathematics and Computation, Chaos, Solitons and Fractals, Dynamics of Continuous, Discrete and Impulsive Systems, Acta Automatica Sinica, Journal of Control Theory and Applications, Acta Electronica Sinica, Control and Decision, and Journal of Engineering Mathematics